

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPONENTS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Annotation: This article contains opinions about the scientific-theoretical and pedagogical-psychological components of the professional training of future music education teachers. Pedagogical conditions of music education were also discussed.

Key words: Music education, component, professional activity, pedagogical activity, scientific analysis, methodology.

Introduction.

The current development of science, technology, production and technology spheres determines the image of modern society. The most important feature of modern society is globalization in all its spheres. Globalization itself requires rapid movement, immediate acquisition of necessary information, their processing and effective implementation. Only personnel who are knowledgeable in their field, have acquired professional skills at a high level, and have rich experience and skills will have the opportunity to move in this way. Therefore, it is appropriate to take into account this demand of the time during the training of personnel in educational institutions.

Studying and analyzing the qualification requirements for the professional competence of pedagogues in all areas of continuing education, the following problems are evident in this regard:

- the disproportion between the modern requirements for the professional competence of pedagogues and the practical actions being taken to prepare educational institutions for professional activity;
- the fact that most graduates of pedagogical universities do not have the methodologically necessary preparation for organizing professional activities in educational institutions;
- modern pedagogical conditions for the formation of professional competence of pedagogues are not established on the basis of a comprehensive system;
- lack of professional and innovative competence of teachers working in general education schools.

It is known that one of the necessary factors that ensure the free and independent practical activity of future pedagogues in professional activity is based on the formation of professional and pedagogical competence in them. In this, the unique structure of pedagogical competence, the stages of its formation, and the development and implementation of effective mechanisms of using modern forms and methods of teaching in this process are of great importance. Therefore, we decided to choose the topic of the project work in this direction

The profession of pedagogy is an honorable one, but it is also a very complicated profession, because it is these pedagogues who educate and raise the youth who will be the strength of the nation, the state, and the hope of tomorrow. Pedagogical profession is called reformist and managerial profession at the same time. In order to manage the development of a person, one must have ability, competence, in a word, competence. Therefore, the concept of the teacher's professional competence represents his theoretical and practical preparation and high-level skills to implement pedagogical activities.

Currently, great attention is paid to the teaching technology in the formation of professional competence. The teaching technologies developed and used by the teaching staff of higher educational institutions are a component of the educational system for determining and educating the professional competence of the future specialist, for the initial creation of a professional basis for acquiring the profession, for the high level of professional activity. It helps in the gradual formation of theoretical, practical and motivational preparation and ability to increase.

Recently, the concept of "competence" has been widely used in psychological and pedagogical literature, in the scientific works of many pedagogic scientists. A competent approach to the education system began to take shape in foreign literature in the 60s of the last century. The concept of "competence" is an ever-growing classification of a person, and it is the ability to solve problems in real life situations, the ability to mobilize one's knowledge, educational and life experiences, values and interests. This concept is how to behave in unconventional or unexpected situations, how to communicate, how to take a new path in interactions with opponents, how to perform ambiguous tasks, how to use conflicting information, how to always develop and complex processes. shows the need for theoretical knowledge about how to act.

According to the tradition formed in Western countries, the professional qualification of a specialist is measured by his competence, and the educational system is measured by the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications. In foreign countries, in accordance with tradition, specialty (qualification) standards are developed, which are considered to be a characteristic feature of the knowledge and skills of the worker. This standard only records the result (what should be achieved). Competence requires constantly enriching one's knowledge, learning new information, feeling the demands of this day and age, the ability to search for new knowledge, process it and apply it in one's practical work. A competent specialist knows how to use the methods and methods that he has mastered in solving problems, which are suitable for this particular situation, he can selectively use the methods that are suitable for the current situation, he can reject those that do not fit the problem, acquires skills such as critical thinking. Getting acquainted with the content of theoretical sources, studying the activities of educational institutions and analyzing the evidence showed that there are a number of contradictions in the formation of professional competence of teachers of vocational education, in particular:

- between the level of mature specialist education of a graduate of a higher educational institution and the normative requirements for the modernized content and volume of the State Education Standard and the level of realization of his personal capabilities;
- between traditional and innovative methods used in the process of formation of professional competence of teachers in higher education institutions;

- between the activities of higher education institutions aimed at pedagogical support in the formation of the teacher's personality and professional competence, and the mechanism and laws of the development of the process of training a teacher as a future teacher;

- between the fact that the possibilities of integration of the pedagogical series of subjects with general professional and specialized subjects in terms of forming the personal and professional competence of the teacher are not used enough;

- it is possible to point out the contradictions between scientific and technical development, increasing demands of a modernized society towards a skilled pedagogue, and teachers' lack of readiness to work in the conditions of self-development of the main part of forming their professional competence.

One of the ways to eliminate such contradictions is to form professional competences of future teachers. To form the professional competence of future teachers, to create the necessary pedagogical conditions to ensure their professional and personal development in educational institutions, to modernize the content and structure of teacher training, to determine their psychological and pedagogical conditions, and to control and evaluate its quality. determines the main goal of the formation of specialist competence through development. An important factor in improving the educational process is closely related to the formation of the professional competence of teachers at a high level in the educational system. Therefore, it is determined that one of the urgent tasks is to create the theoretical and practical foundations of the process of forming the professional competence of teachers based on the effective use of the opportunities of modern educational technologies and the created educational methodological complexes. In this regard, the scientific justification of new approaches that ensure the level of professional competence required from the period of training of teachers in higher education institutions has become an urgent task.

A direct study of the content of education in practice in foreign countries regarding the professional training of specialists showed that in Western countries the main place is occupied by the level of competence of the specialist. According to the nature of the national education system of our republic, the minimum requirements of the content of education are based on knowledge, skills and qualifications. If we look at the etymological analysis of the concepts "competent" and "competence", we can understand that they did not arise by chance. Competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by the teacher, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Competence is expressed by the teacher's acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of personal and socially significant professional activities and their ability to apply them in professional activities.

Due to the fact that the educational content is grouped into blocks of subjects in the curriculum (for all subjects), interdisciplinary (for a set of subjects) and subjects (for a specific subject), we recognize the following three levels of competence :

- basic competence (according to the humanitarian, socio-economic content of education);

- interdisciplinary competence (according to the specific framework of educational subjects and educational blocks of general professional training);

- competence in one subject (subject) (according to having a clear and certain opportunity within a special academic subject).

Thus, basic competence is determined at the level of educational blocks and academic subjects for each stage of pedagogical education. In determining the order of basic competence, the essence of social and personal experience in accordance with the main goals of professional pedagogical education, the main types that allow the acquisition of life skills in the process of organizing professional activity in social society are of great importance. From this point of view, they are divided into the following types of competence:

1. Comprehensive - meaningful competence. It is related to the value directions of the teacher, his ability to feel and understand the social existence, to find an independent way of life, to understand his role and place in the social society, to set a clear goal in the organization of actions. and decision-making competence, competence related to worldview, which provides a mechanism for self-determination for the teacher in educational and other situations. The individual educational direction of the teacher and the general program of his life activity depend on this competence.

2. Socio-cultural competence. The scope of knowledge and activity experience that the teacher needs to master in depth is the characteristics of national and universal cultures, the spiritual and moral foundations of human and human life, the cultural foundations of family and social traditions, science in human life and the role of religion, their influence on material existence, knowledge about life and recreation, for example, knowing the methods of effective organization of free time.

3. Educational - cognitive competence is a set of independent thinking competences consisting of elements of the teacher's logical, methodological and social activity related to the specific objects being studied, according to the purpose includes knowledge and skills of knowledge, activity planning, analysis of its content, reflection, personal evaluation of the activity. In relation to the studied objects, teachers acquire creative skills, that is, obtaining knowledge directly from existence, methods of action and heuristic methods of solving problems in non-standard situations.

4. Information acquisition competence. With the help of audio-video tools and information technologies, the skills of independent research, analysis and selection of necessary information, their modification, storage and transmission are formed.

5. Communicative competence. Interactions with students, their methods, mastery of the language that takes a priority place in the communication process, skills of working in groups, and knowledge of organizing and conducting various spiritual and educational activities in the team include .

6. Social-active competence in citizenship (citizen, observer, voter, representative), social-labor field (consumer, buyer, customer, producer rights), family relations and obligations, economic and legal issues, professional, as well as , means acquiring knowledge and experience in determining one's personal position (in particular, analyzing the current situation in the labor market, the ability to act in pursuit of personal and social interests, knowing the etiquette of labor and civil relations).

7. Competence related to practical activity means the ability to move from one state of action to another state of action, to apply actions and actions in new situations, to quickly find direction in new information.

A graduate of a higher educational institution with a pedagogic qualification in the field of vocational education: readiness to carry out pedagogical activities in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards, a modern education that ensures a high level of

theoretical and practical training to use teaching technologies, to participate in the development of educational programs, to be responsible for their full implementation in accordance with the curriculum and educational process, to improve the knowledge, skills and abilities of learners to organize supervision, to prepare them for the application of the acquired knowledge in practical activities and to supervise the independent work of learners, to create the base of the teaching-methodical equipment of specific educational subjects, to participate in the scientific-methodical activities of the educational institution, perform the duties of a class leader, organize and conduct educational work with students, ensure the implementation of educational plans and programs, ensure educational discipline, observe the rights and freedoms of students, o He should improve his professional skills. Based on the understanding that professional competence is based on the reflection of the specialist's activity and the important characteristics of its internal structure, the structure of professional competence can be clarified in terms of describing its main components.

Special or functional professional competence is the ability to carry out activities at a high professional level. Special professional competence consists not only of special knowledge, but also of the implementation of this knowledge; Social competence is knowing how to carry out additional activities, knowing how to cooperate; personal competence - knowing the ways of self-development and self-presentation (the specialist plans his activities, makes independent decisions, works with information and on himself). Individual competence is knowing how to manage oneself, preparing for professional development and creating professional innovations. At the same time, the teacher's knowledge should be enriched with news, psychological and pedagogical qualities should be at a high level.

CONCLUSION

An important factor in improving the process of music education is closely related to the formation of professional competence of teachers in the educational system. Therefore, it is determined that one of the urgent tasks is to create the theoretical and practical foundations of the process of forming the professional competence of teachers based on the effective use of the opportunities of modern educational technologies and the created educational methodological complexes.

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